

Table S1

Key Characteristics and Main Findings of the Analyzed Studies

Author(s), (year), country, and type of study	Aim(s)	Participants	Parental involvement measure & instrument	Self-efficacy measure & instrument	Main findings
Affuso et al. (2017) ITALY Longitudinal	To examine the contribution of school-related parental monitoring, self-determined motivation, and academic self-efficacy to academic achievement across time.	<i>N</i> = 501 family triads Students (6 th -9 th grade) Gender: 281 F, 220 M Age state: 266 early adolescents and 235 middle adolescents <i>M</i> _{age} early adolescents = 11.17 <i>M</i> _{age} middle adolescents = 14.32 Parents <i>M</i> _{age} mothers = 41.76 <i>M</i> _{age} fathers = 44.69	School-related parental monitoring using the <i>Parental Monitoring Scale</i> ¹ .	Academic self-efficacy using the <i>Academic Perceived Self-Efficacy Scale</i> ² : (1) perceived capability to successfully master different curricular areas (2) perceived capacity for self-regulating learning activities.	Early adolescents had higher scores for SR-PM. Correlation analyses School-related maternal monitoring (MR) at T1 was positively correlated to academic self-efficacy at T1 ($r = .35, p < .001$) and T2 ($r = .36, p < .001$). School-related paternal monitoring (FR) at T1 was positively correlated to academic self-efficacy at T1 ($r = .29, p < .001$) and T2 ($r = .26, p < .001$). Structural equation modeling The analysis of the indirect effects showed that maternal and paternal monitoring (SR-PM) at T1 predicted academic performance at T1 through academic self-efficacy ($\beta = .12, p < .001$ and $\beta = .13, p < .001$ for preadolescents and adolescents, respectively), and affected academic performance at T2 through academic self-efficacy at T2 ($\beta = .02, p < .05$ for preadolescents and adolescents). Results also showed the indirect effect of academic self-efficacy at T1 ($\beta = .03, p < .01$ for early and middle adolescents) on academic self-efficacy at T2 via academic achievement at T1b.
Affuso et al. (2023) ITALY Longitudinal	To investigate the contribution of teacher support and parental monitoring to academic performance over three years, testing the mediating role of self-determined motivation and academic self-efficacy and establishing whether the role of teachers and parents varies over time.	Students <i>N</i> = 429 (9 th grade) Gender: 218 F, 201 M <i>M</i> _{age} = 14.34	Parental monitoring using the <i>Parental Monitoring Scale-Revised</i> ³ : Maternal and paternal knowledge of the child's whereabouts, activities, and peers.	Academic self-efficacy using the <i>Academic Perceived Self-Efficacy Scale</i> ² : (1) perceived capability to successfully master different curricular areas (2) perceived capacity for self-regulating learning activities.	Females had higher scores for parental monitoring. Correlation analyses Maternal monitoring at T1 was positively correlated to academic self-efficacy at T2 ($r = .36, p < .001$) and T3 ($r = .28, p < .001$). Paternal monitoring at T1 was positively correlated to academic self-efficacy at T2 ($r = .38, p < .001$) and T3 ($r = .36, p < .001$). Structural equation modeling A direct positive effect of maternal and paternal monitoring at T1 on adolescents' academic self-efficacy was observed at T2 ($\beta = .36, p < .001$) and T3 ($\beta = .10, p < .05$). On the other hand, indirect positive significant effects of maternal and paternal monitoring (T1) on academic performance at T3 were observed through academic self-efficacy at T2 and T3 for girls ($\beta = .05, p < .001$) and boys ($\beta = .04, p < .001$).
Andretta et al. (2017) NORTHERN IRLAND Cross-sectional	To identify perceived parental security profiles and examine differences across profiles with regard to self-esteem and three domains of self-efficacy (i.e., social, emotional, and academic).	Students <i>N</i> = 1126 (8 th -12 th grade) Gender: 39% F, 61% M <i>M</i> _{age} : no data	Perceived parental security using the <i>Inventory of Parent and Peer Attachment-Revised</i> (IPPA- R) ⁴ : Parental trust, communication, and alienation.	Assessment of self-efficacy based on a comprehensive conception in three domains using the <i>Self-Efficacy Questionnaire for Children</i> (SEQ-C) ⁵ : Academic, emotional and social self-efficacy.	Correlation analyses Significant positive correlations were observed between academic, social and emotional self-efficacy and parental communication ($r = .36; r = .16; r = .13$, respectively; $p < .001$) and parental confidence ($r = .38; r = .16; r = .18$, respectively; $p < .001$) and negative correlations for parental alienation ($r = -.34; r = -.16; r = -.28$, respectively; $p < .001$). Model-based clustering (parental communication, confidence, and alienation) led to the identification of five perceived parental security profiles: (a) high security, (b) moderately high security, (c) average security, (d) moderately low security, and (e) low security. Adolescents with high security and low security profiles, respectively, reported the highest and lowest levels of self-esteem and self-efficacy ($0.48 \leq \text{Cohen's } d \leq 1.67$). Statistically significant differences were found between these profiles with respect to three domains of self-efficacy: academic ($F_{(4,1114)} = 44.97; p < .001$), emotional ($F_{(4,1114)} = 13.56; p < .001$) and social ($F_{(4,1114)} = 9.42; p < .001$). Adolescents with a high parental security profile reported higher levels of self-efficacy on all three dimensions, whereas those with a low security profile had the lowest scores, although effect sizes were minimally interpretable.

Author(s), (year), country, and type of study	Aim(s)	Participants	Parental involvement measure & instrument	Self-efficacy measure & instrument	Main findings
Ben-Tov & Romi (2019) ISRAEL Cross-sectional	To examine relationships between parents' involvement as related to their identification with school and their alertness to school environment and students regarding four variables: Attitudes toward school, Social adjustment, Self-efficacy and Academic achievement.	Students N = 343 (4th-6th grade students) Gender: 149 F, 181 M M _{age} : No data Parents N = 339	Parental involvement using the <i>Parents' Involvement Questionnaire</i> (PIQ) ⁶ : Parenting, student learning at school, school-home communication, and collaboration with community.	Learning, self-regulation and social efficacy using the <i>Self-Efficacy Questionnaire</i> ⁷ .	Structural equation modeling The results point to parental involvement would present a low prediction with a tendency to statistical significance of their children's attitudes ($\beta = .09+$) towards school, studies and teachers –being greater the impact of involvement in school ($\beta = .93$) and in the community ($\beta = .87$)–, and to a positive direct effect of these on students' self-efficacy ($\beta = .44$).
Cross et al. (2019) UNITED STATES Cross-sectional	To examine how adolescents' perceptions of parental educational expectations and their parents' academic socialization messages (i.e., shame/pressure and effort) relate to adolescents' academic self-efficacy.	N = 148 Latino parent-adolescent dyads Students (8 th -9 th grade) Gender: 53% F, 47% M M _{age} : No data Parents 85.8% mothers, 14.2% fathers 90.5% foreign-born M _{age} = 40.45	-Perceived parental educational expectations using the <i>Perceived Parental Academic Support Scale</i> (PPASS) ⁸ . -Parental academic socialization: A) Shame/pressure socialization (items used in previous study). B) Effort socialization through the <i>Effort subscale</i> of the <i>Educational Socialization Scale</i> ⁹ .	Academic self-efficacy based on the measures used in a previous study: Confidence in their ability to tackle academic challenges.	Correlation analyses No significant correlations of academic self-efficacy with shame/pressure academic socialization or parental effort socialization were found, but significant correlations were found with parental educational expectations ($r = .57, p < .001$). Multiple hierarchical regression analyses Both shame/pressure and effortful academic socialization moderated the relationship between self-efficacy and parental expectations. The positive association between youths' perceived parental educational expectations was greater when parents exerted less pressure/shame ($\beta = .75, p < .001$ vs. $\beta = .43, p < .001$) and provided fewer effort socialization messages ($\beta = .75, p < .001$ vs. $\beta = .46, p < .001$).
Dong et al. (2020) CHINA Cross-sectional	To examine the mediation effects of adolescents' academic self-efficacy and academic value between parental involvement and academic emotions.	N = 391 family triads Students (5 th -12 th grade) Gender: 197 F, 194 M M _{age} = 13.57 Parents No data	Students' perceived parental involvement using the <i>Parents's Involvement in Children's Learning Scale</i> ¹⁰ .	Academic self-efficacy through the <i>Questionnaire of Academic Self-Efficacy</i> ¹¹ : (1) academic self-efficacy of behavior (students' confidence in whether they can adopt suitable learning strategies to achieve learning goals) and (2) academic self-efficacy of ability (students' confidence in whether they can finish school, earn good grades, and avoid academic failure).	Correlation analyses Significant positive correlations were observed between parental involvement and behavioral ($r = .31, p < .001$) and ability ($r = .39, p < .001$) academic self-efficacy. Structural equation modeling Ability self-efficacy mediated the relationship between parental involvement and academic enjoyment ($\beta = .29, p < .05$), while behavioral self-efficacy mediated the relationship with academic boredom ($\beta = -.12, p < .05$).

Author(s), (year), country, and type of study	Aim(s)	Participants	Parental involvement measure & instrument	Self-efficacy measure & instrument	Main findings
Grijalva-Quiñonez et al. (2020) MÉXICO Cross-sectional	To analyze the relationship between the types of parental involvement in homework, psychological resources, and academic achievement in Mexican elementary students.	Students N = 823 (5 th -6 th grade) Gender: 51% F, 49% M M _{age} = 11.12 Parents No data.	Parental involvement in children's homework using the <i>Parental Autonomy Support and Control in Homework</i> ¹²	Academic self-efficacy using the <i>Patterns Adaptive Learning Scales (PALS)</i> ¹³ . Students' self-perceptions about their efficacy to achieve academic goals with the <i>Self-Efficacy for Self-Regulated Learning Scale</i> ¹⁴	Males perceived more parental control in homework. Correlation analyses A positive correlation was reported between academic self-efficacy and perceived parental autonomy support ($r = .41, p < .01$), especially in school tasks, and a negative correlation with parental control ($r = -.23, p < .01$). Structural equation modeling Parent autonomy support positively influenced academic self-efficacy ($\beta = .53, p < .001$), while parental control had a negative effect ($\beta = -.27, p < .001$). Indirectly, autonomy support improved academic performance through its impact on self-efficacy ($\beta = .18, p < .001$), while parental control decreased it ($\beta = -.16, p < .001$). In addition, reciprocal effects were identified: academic self-efficacy reduced parental control ($\beta = -.18, p < .001$) and increased autonomy support ($\beta = .37, p < .001$).
Huang et al. (2021) CHINA Cross-sectional	To examine the direct effects of different dimensions of parental involvement on students' mathematics achievement and to consider the multiple mediating roles of students' mathematics self-efficacy and mental health in the parental involvement and mathematics achievement.	Students N = 2866 (6 th grade) Gender: 46.76% F, 53.24% M M _{age} = 11.57 Parents No data.	Parental involvement using the <i>Parent-School Interaction Questionnaire</i> ¹⁵ : - Cognitive involvement - Behavioral involvement - Personal involvement.	Mathematics self-efficacy using the short form of the <i>Mathematics Self-Efficacy Scale</i> ¹⁶ .	Correlation analyses Statistically significant positive correlations were observed between self-efficacy perception and cognitive ($r = .22, p < .001$), personal ($r = .20, p < .001$) and behavioral ($r = .23, p < .001$) parental involvement. Structural equation modeling The mediation model showed a direct and significant positive effect of cognitive parental involvement -e.g., search for learning materials- on self-efficacy in mathematics ($\beta = .16, p < .001$) and an indirect effect through this on academic performance in that subject ($\beta = .06, p < .001$).
Kristensen et al. (2023) NORWAY Longitudinal	To investigate whether perceived social support from peers, parents and teachers influence grade point average (GPA) directly or indirectly through adolescent students' entity intelligence beliefs (EIB) and academic self-efficacy (ASE).	Students N = 750 (8 th -10 th grade) Gender: 51% F, 49% M M _{age} : No data	Parental academic support using the <i>Parental School Support Scale</i> ¹⁷ .	Academic self-efficacy (items used in a previous study): Perceived school-related tasks, skills, and performance.	Correlation analyses A positive and significant correlation was found between parental support and perceived self-efficacy measured in terms of ability ($r = .42, p < .001$). Structural equation modeling A direct positive effect of parental academic support perceived by the adolescents on their academic self-efficacy could be observed ($\beta = .15, p < .05$), but an indirect effect through this on their average grade two years later was not appreciated.
Liu et al. (2019) CHINA Cross-sectional	To examine a complex model linking parental support, homework self-efficacy, emotion regulation strategies, and homework emotions in Chinese children.	Students N = 832 (4 th -5 th grade) Gender: 390 F, 442 M M _{age} = 10.25	Parents' supportive behaviors using the <i>Parents' Need Supportive Behaviour Questionnaire</i> (PNSBQ) ¹⁸ : Parents' support of autonomy, competence, and relatedness.	Homework self-efficacy in mathematics using the <i>Homework Self-Efficacy Questionnaire</i> ¹⁹ .	Correlation analyses A significant positive correlation was found between homework self-efficacy and parental support ($r = .50, p < .001$). Measurement model The results showed that parental support perceived by the children positively and directly impacted their perceived homework self-efficacy. On the other hand, parental support indirectly predicted homework-related emotions through the mediating effect of homework self-efficacy ($c^2/df = 2.24, RMSEA = 0.04, SRMR = 0.05, CFI = 0.94, TLI = 0.94$).

Author(s), (year), country, and type of study	Aim(s)	Participants	Parental involvement measure & instrument	Self-efficacy measure & instrument	Main findings
<p>Lv et al. (2018) CHINA Cross-sectional</p>	<p>To identify self-efficacy profiles in different domains (academic, emotional and social) and examine whether different dimensions of parental involvement were associated with these profiles.</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 1998 parent-child dyads Students (4th-6th grade) Gender: 954 F, 1044 M M_{age} = 10.22 Parents M_{age} mothers = 38.01 M_{age} fathers = 40.31</p>	<p>Parental involvement practices using the <i>Parental Involvement Questionnaire</i> (PIQ)²⁰:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Father/mother monitoring - Father/mother learning-assistance - Father/mother-child communication - Father/mother-child activity - Father/mother-school contact - Father/mother parental educational aspirations. 	<p>Assessment of self-efficacy from a comprehensive conception in three domains using the <i>Self-Efficacy Questionnaire for Children</i> (SEQ-C)⁵: Academic, emotional and social self-efficacy</p>	<p>Correlation analyses Statistically significant positive correlations were observed between academic, social and emotional self-efficacy and parental monitoring (fathers: $r = .09^{**}$, $r = .06^{**}$, $r = .08^{*}$; mothers: $r = .09^{**}$, $r = .08^{**}$, $r = .06^{*}$), participation in extracurricular activities (fathers: $r = .14^{**}$, $r = .11^{**}$, $r = .09^{**}$; mothers: $r = .15^{**}$, $r = .13^{**}$, $r = .10^{**}$), and communication and interest in children (fathers: $r = .10^{**}$, $r = .06^{**}$, $r = .05^{*}$; mothers: $r = .14^{**}$, $r = .13^{**}$, $r = .10^{**}$). Academic and emotional self-efficacy correlated positively with parents' contact with the school (fathers: $r = .05^{*}$, $r = .05^{*}$; mothers: $r = .09^{**}$, $r = .06^{*}$). Only mother's contact did so with social self-efficacy ($r = .06^{*}$). Academic self-efficacy correlated significantly and positively with homework support from father ($r = .08^{**}$) and mother ($r = .07^{**}$). Finally, significant and positive correlations appear between mothers' and fathers' expectations and children's academic ($r = .15^{**}$, $r = .16$) and social ($r = .09^{**}$, $r = .06^{**}$) self-efficacy. $^{**}p < .01$; $^{*}p < .05$</p> <p>Self-efficacy profiles Five student self-efficacy profiles were identified: very low self-efficacy, low self-efficacy, low emotional self-efficacy, moderate self-efficacy, and high self-efficacy. Only mother-child communication was associated with a greater likelihood of the child being in the high self-efficacy group [1.59 (0.86-2.95)] versus the low emotional self-efficacy group [0.86(0.42-1.77)]. Parental monitoring and contact with the school were not associated with students' belonging to any of the five self-efficacy profiles.</p>
<p>Rodríguez et al. (2017) SPAIN Cross-sectional</p>	<p>To analyze how the perception of parents' beliefs is related to children's beliefs, their involvement in mathematical tasks and their performance.</p>	<p>Students <i>N</i> = 897 (5th-6th grade) Gender: 49.8% F, 50.2% M M_{age} = 10.77</p>	<p>Perceived parental involvement using the <i>Family Involvement Questionnaire</i>²¹:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interest in the progress of children. - Parents help with academic tasks - Parents' expectations. 	<p>Math self-efficacy using the <i>Math Self-Efficacy Subscale (Inventory of Attitudes toward Mathematics)</i>²²</p>	<p>Correlational analyses A significant positive correlation was observed between mathematics self-efficacy with perceived parental task support ($r = .27$, $p < .01$), interest in children's progress ($r = .17$, $p < .01$) and expectations ($r = .42$, $p < .01$).</p> <p>Structural equation modeling An effect of homework support ($\beta = .06$, $p < .05$) and high parental expectations ($\beta = .40$, $p < .001$) on math self-efficacy was seen and this, in turn, positively impacted math achievement ($\beta = .22$, $p < .001$). However, structural equation analysis did not demonstrate an effect of parental interest in children's progress on mathematical self-efficacy.</p>
<p>Shi et al. (2024) CHINA Longitudinal</p>	<p>To examine the implications of parents' constructive versus unconstructive involvement for children's academic and emotional functioning over time, with attention to the role of two distinct homework contexts that feature contrasting child behaviors – where children demonstrated helplessness versus mastery.</p>	<p><i>N</i> = 370 mother-child dyads Students (4th grade) Gender: 55 % F, 45% M M_{age} = 9.90 Mothers M_{age} = 40.86</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mothers' constructive homework involvement: positive emotions, autonomy support, and mastery-oriented teaching - Mothers' unconstructive homework involvement: negative emotions, control, and performance-oriented teaching - Mothers' time commitment to homework (measures from previous studies). 	<p>Homework self-efficacy using different items adopted from a previous study.</p>	<p>Correlation analyses Significant negative correlations were observed between mothers' time spent on homework and children's academic self-efficacy in the short ($r = -.18$, $p < .001$) and long term ($r = -.27$, $p < .001$). On the other hand, mothers' constructive involvement was positively correlated with students' short- ($r = .18$, $p < .01$) and long-term ($r = .27$, $p < .001$) homework self-efficacy in helplessness contexts. In contrast, parents' nonconstructive involvement showed negative correlations with self-efficacy in both helplessness ($r = -.27$, $p < .001$, and $r = -.26$, $p < .001$) and mastery ($r = -.21$, $p < .001$, and $r = -.18$, $p < .01$) homework contexts.</p> <p>Structural equation modeling In the long term, mothers' constructive involvement significantly predicted self-efficacy in helplessness contexts ($\beta = .21$, $p < .01$), whereas non-constructive involvement predicted lower self-efficacy ($\beta = -.16$, $p < .05$). In mastery contexts, constructive involvement was not predictive of children's self-efficacy.</p>

Author(s), (year), country, and type of study	Aim(s)	Participants	Parental involvement measure & instrument	Self-efficacy measure & instrument	Main findings
Sun et al. (2020) CHINA Cross-sectional	To investigate the association of perceived parental warmth with math engagement among Chinese students.	Students <i>N</i> = 1132 (9 th and 11 th grade) Gender: 577 F, 555 M <i>M</i> _{age} = 15.92	Perceived parental and maternal warmth using the <i>Parenting Warmth Scale</i> ²³ and <i>Egna Minnen Beträffande Uppfostran scale</i> (EMBU) ²⁴ .	Math self-efficacy using the <i>Motivational and Self-Regulated Learning Questionnaire</i> ²⁵ .	Correlation analyses Significant positive correlations were observed between children's perception of warmth on the part of their mothers and fathers and their self-efficacy in mathematics ($r = .21$; $r = .21$) ($p < .01$). Significant positive correlations were also found between the perception of self-efficacy and the three basic psychological needs (autonomy: $r = .24$; competence: $r = .33$; relatedness: $r = .22$) ($p < .01$). Structural equation model Mothers' and fathers' warmth has an indirect positive effect on math engagement through children's perceived self-efficacy in this domain and satisfaction of their need for competence ($\beta = .006$, $p < .01$; $\beta = .06$, $p < .001$).
Thomas et al. (2019) BELGIUM Longitudinal	To explore the relationship among parental involvement in the first year of middle school, students' school achievement and several dimensions of students' self-regulated learning.	Students <i>N</i> = 5939 (7 th grade) Gender: 47% F, 53% M <i>M</i> _{age} : No data	Perceived parental involvement (items used in previous studies).	Academic self-efficacy using the <i>Academic Perceived Self-Efficacy Scale</i> ² : ability to plan and organize academic activities, structure learning environments, and motivate oneself to do schoolwork.	Correlation analyses Parental involvement presented a significant positive correlation with academic self-efficacy ($r = .26$, $p < .01$). Multiple mediation modeling Parental involvement had a direct effect on perceived self-efficacy ($\beta = .14$, $p < .001$) and an indirect positive impact on academic performance through this ($ab=0.02$, 99% CI [0.01, 0.02]).
Xu et al. (2017) CHINA Cross-sectional	(1) To explore how Chinese parental psychological control relates to the test anxiety of their adolescent sons and daughters. (2) To examine whether adolescents' academic self-efficacy mediated the effect of parental psychological control on the adolescents' test anxiety.	Students <i>N</i> = 401 (15-18 years old) Gender: 243 F, 158 M <i>M</i> _{age} = 16.13	Parental and maternal psychological control using the <i>Psychological Control Scale</i> ²⁶ .	Academic self-efficacy using the <i>Questionnaire of Academic Self-efficacy</i> ¹¹ : Academic competence efficacy and academic behavior efficacy.	Correlation analyses A significant negative correlation was found between parental psychological control and perceived self-efficacy in adolescents ($r = -.21$ for fathers, $p < .001$; $r = -.16$, $p < .01$ for mothers). Structural equation modeling Self-efficacy partially mediated the relationship between perceived psychological control and test anxiety ($\chi^2_{(1)} = 14.32$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2_{(1)} = 17.59$, $p < .001$).
Yap & Baharudin (2015) MALAYSIA Cross-sectional	To examine the mediation roles of academic self-efficacy, social self-efficacy, and emotional self-efficacy on the relationships between parental involvement (i.e., paternal involvement and maternal involvement) and subjective well-being (i.e., positive affect, negative affect, and life satisfaction).	Students <i>N</i> = 802 (11 th grade) Gender: 55% F, 45% M <i>M</i> _{age} = 16	Perceived paternal and maternal involvement using the <i>Father Involvement Scale</i> ²⁷ .	Assessment of self-efficacy based on a comprehensive conception in three domains using the <i>Self-Efficacy Questionnaire for Children</i> (SEQ-C) ⁵ : Academic, emotional and social self-efficacy.	Correlation analyses Significant positive correlations were found between mothers' and fathers' involvement and students' perceived academic ($r = .31$; $r = .23$), social ($r = .30$; $r = .27$), and emotional ($r = .26$; $r = .28$) self-efficacy ($p < .01$). These correlations were also found between academic, social, and emotional self-efficacy with life satisfaction ($r = .27$, $p < .01$; $r = .12$, $p < .05$; and $r = .21$, $p < .01$) and positive affect ($r = .37$, $r = .48$ and $r = .48$; $p < .01$). A negative correlation was found between academic and emotional self-efficacy and negative affect ($r = -.10$, $p < .05$; $r = -.14$, $p < .01$). Multiple mediating model Academic self-efficacy (AA) and social self-efficacy (AS) were mediators of the relationships between maternal and paternal involvement and adolescents' positive affect (AA: $CI_{.95}$.006, .031; $CI_{.95}$.004, .024. AS: $CI_{.95}$.019, .053; $CI_{.95}$.011, .048), whereas only academic self-efficacy mediated the effect of maternal and paternal involvement and life satisfaction ($CI_{.95}$.031, .086; $CI_{.95}$.015, .068).

Note. To facilitate the reading of the information contained in the table and to help locate the instruments for measuring parental involvement and student self-efficacy mentioned in each of the articles included in the systematic review, the references of these instruments are included below.

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